

THE INTERPRETATION OF THE DREAM MOTIF IN FOLK SONGS

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Abstract: Folk songs are considered one of the most ancient and richest genres of folklore. Therefore, the period of their creation is rooted in antiquity and mythological perceptions. Songs initially emerged as seasonal ritual folklore specimens and, over time, gradually developed into a fully formed genre with distinct characteristics of their own. Folk songs have undergone an evolutionary process ranging from mythological perception to poetic thinking. For this reason, in the content and essence of songs, in their motifs and structure, as well as in the symbols and metaphors associated with them, we can trace the marks of this long historical process. When studying the interpretation of leading themes and motifs in folk songs, it is necessary to examine not only their place within the song structure, but also their mythological roots as a whole. From this perspective, the passages related to dreams in folk songs and the dream motif have been very little studied.

When discussing the dream motif in folk songs, it is appropriate to dwell on two aspects in particular. The first is the harmony between metaphors and symbols in folk songs and the symbols and metaphors found in dreams. The second aspect concerns the relationship between dream and myth, and its harmony with the relationship between song and myth. In our article, through the analysis of the dream motif in folk songs, we examine such issues in detail.

Keywords: Folk songs, dream motif, myth, mythological perception, structure, image, symbol, metaphor, artistic interpretation.

Before speaking about the relationship between dreams and songs — more precisely, about the influence of dreams on the creation, content, and artistry of folk songs — it should be noted that both of them are historical-typological, vital, and enduring phenomena common to all humanity. That is, just as there is no person in the world who has never had a dream, there is likewise no person who, even without a gift for singing, has never at least hummed a song. However, our research shows that, however vast Uzbek folk lyric songs may be in volume and however widespread in terms of composition and performance, examples in which dreams are directly mentioned are rarely encountered among them.¹

For instance, in the song collection titled "*Oq olma, qizil olma*" compiled and published by scholar Muzayyana Alaviya, dreams are not mentioned even once. As exceptions, we may cite the following examples:

Singlim sahar-saharda

Tush ko 'ribdi, yor-yor.

Tushida bir qarchig'ay

Xush ko 'ribdi, yor-yor.

¹ Алавия М. Ўзбек халқ кўшиқлари. – Тошкент, 1959; Гулёр. Фарғона халқ кўшиқлари. – Тошкент: Адабиёт ва санъат, 1967; Оқ олма, қизил олма. Ўзбек халқ кўшиқлари. – Тошкент: Адабиёт ва санъат, 1972; Тўй муборак: Ёр-ёр / Нашрга тайёрловчи Охунжон Сафаров. – Тошкент: Маънавият, 2000.

The interpretation of this dream is self-evident to the listeners of the song, requiring no explanation. For in Uzbek folk tradition, when an unmarried girl sees a bird in her dream, it is customarily interpreted as a sign that she will soon be given in marriage. Nevertheless, within the course of the song, the dream is interpreted as well:

*Tushidagi qarchig'ay
Birov bo'lgay, yor-yor.
Birov-birov demanglar,
Kuyov bo'lgay, yor-yor.*

Songs in which dreams are directly mentioned are also very rarely encountered in the rich repertoire of professional folk bards (*bakhshis*) and *khalfa* singers. Among the songs in the repertoire of renowned professional *khalfa* singers of Khorezm, the following lines are directly connected with dreams:

*Kunduz bo'lsa, ishlaganda ishingman,
Kecha bo'lsa, uxlaganda tushingman,
Shirin jondan kechib yurgan kishingman,
Yoqma, bola, o'z yonganim oz emas...
Oqshom tushimda bir guli rayhoni ko'ribman,
Men ul guli rayhon birlan birga yuribman...
Juma kecha ko'rgan tush hikmatlidir, yor-yor,
Yomon ishi doimo minnatlidir, yor-yor.²
Xush uyquda yotsam, kirar tushima,
Seskanib uyg'onsam, tushar yodima,
Oh deganda yosh aylanar ko'zima,
Kelmadi, kelmadi, nechun kelmadi?³*

Although examples in which dreams are directly mentioned — such lines as these — represent but a single drop from the vast ocean of folk songs, they nonetheless allow us to draw certain conclusions and form scholarly hypotheses regarding the relationship between dreams and songs.

² Анаш халфа. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси, 2006. – Б.18, 47.

³ Ожиза. Шеър ва дostonлар. – Тошкент, 2003. – Б.14.

First, in one of the examples it is stated that a dream seen on a Friday carries wisdom and meaning — a belief that is characteristic of the entire Uzbek people's attitude toward dreams. Second, in these examples, the desires and inner experiences of a beloved person are expressed through the medium of dreams.

It is a truth requiring no proof that people who have fallen in love — young people in particular — dream of their beloved and of matters connected with love. Moreover, among them there were many who grew up in an environment steeped in song and possessed the ability to create new compositions in the manner of folk songs. It may be assumed that such lovers, upon waking from a dream, poured the emotions stirred by that dream into songs.

M. Alaviya, who devoted her entire scholarly and creative life to collecting, publishing, and studying folk songs, repeatedly emphasizes in all her works that the theme of love and romance has always been the dominant subject in folk songs.⁴

Whereas in epics (*dastans*) and fairy tales the dream motif appears actively — frequently serving the function of initiating the plot and sometimes symbolically foreshadowing the future fate of the characters — in folk lyric poetry we observe an entirely different picture.

It may be said that if a researcher wishes to study the influence of the dream phenomenon on folk songs directly — that is, by searching for the word "dream" — their inquiry will prove fruitless from the outset and will lead into a dead end. Yet just as dreams are a world of symbols, folk songs too are equally rich in symbols. Our observations show that the influence of dreams in folk songs is typically present in the "subtext." For this reason, even when dreams are not directly mentioned in them, we find that the very essence of the majority of these songs rests upon dreams and their interpretations. What is significant is that, since the symbols directly conveyed through dreams in folk epics and fairy tales — that is, symbols upon which emphasis is placed — are rooted in mythological thinking, we find no fundamental serious difference between their indirect, unrecorded expression in songs. To substantiate our argument, let us compare the symbols conveyed through dreams in the epics "*Alpomish*" and "*Kuntug'mish*" with the symbols found in folk songs.

When *Alpomish* first falls asleep in a graveyard, the *chiltans* bring together his spirit and the spirit of *Barchin*. A bowl of divine wine (*antahur*) comes to the spirit of *Barchin*. *Barchin* takes the wine in her hand and, not wishing to drink it herself, offers it to *Alpomish* and speaks these words:

Xon to'ram, sizga ne bo'ldi,

Oling, allayor-allayor.

Shunday bo'ldi Barchin so'zi,

Kiyganim gulgun qirmizi,

Aqlingdolar jodu ko'zi,

Qavatida yo'q kanizi,

Kosa berar biyning qizi...⁵

⁴ Қаранг: Алавия М. Ўзбек халқ маросим кўшиқлари. – Тошкент: Фан, 1974.

⁵ Алпомиш. Ўзбек халқ қаҳрамонлик достони / Айтувчи Фозил Йўлдош ўғли. Ёзиб олувчи М.Зарифов. – Тошкент: Шарқ, 1988. – Б.91–92.

In essence, the bowl held by Barchin and the divine wine (*antahur*) within it correspond to the bowl or cup offered to the bride and groom at wedding ceremonies to this day, along with the wedding water it contains. Just as the wine in the epic possesses magical power, the wedding water over which prayers have been recited is likewise understood to carry such power. For this reason, since the marriage vows have not yet been pronounced, Alpomish postpones drinking the wine offered by Barchin — but one day he is bound to drink it.

"If we pay attention to the traces of water cults according to the historical foundations of folk songs," writes A. Musaqulov, "water and its attributes in folk lyrics — dew, a drop, a spring, a well, a canal, a stream, a river, ice, a pond, snow, rain, aquatic plants such as reeds, mint, and trees along the waterside, water creatures such as fish and snakes, water vessels such as a jug, a bowl, and a cup — all of these, in one aspect or another, are connected with the ideas and experiences of love, family, and children."⁶

In folk lyrics, two lovers drinking tea together (wine in epics) serves as a symbol of union, their inability to drink together symbolizes separation, the desire to drink represents the longing of love, the delicacy of the tea vessels symbolizes happiness, and their breaking symbolizes misfortune:

Namanganning yo'llari,

Piyolaning gullari.

Choy ichganda yarashgan

*Bizning yorning qo'llari.*⁷

Since the separation has not yet ended, Alpomish is unable to drink the wine offered by Barchin. As the hero's future fate remains somewhat uncertain, not much time passes between his dreams. While lying in the shepherds' quarters, he sees his second dream at dawn. His spiritual guide (*pir*) appears in the dream and consoles him. At this very same time, the dream seen by Barchin sheds light on their future fate. From the interpretation of Barchin's dream as recounted by her handmaid Suqsuroy:

Qibla betdan bir oy tug'ib kelsalar,

Oy emasdir, ul ham Rasul payg'ambar.

Oy girdinda to'rtta yorug' yulduz bor,

Yulduz emas, to'rt choriyor muqarrar...

Ko'targan burguti bobong Chibori,

Ustida qarchig'ay Hakim shunqori...

⁶ Мусақулов А. Ўзбек халқ кўшиқларининг тарихий асослари. — Тошкент: Фан, 1994. — Б.15.

⁷ Оқ олма, қизил олма. Ўзбек халқ кўшиқлари / Тўпловчи М. Алавия. — Тошкент: Фан, 1972. — Б.86.

*Boychibori yem yemaymi qo'lingnan,
Vakillari savol so'rar tilingnan.
Qochsang, seni nega qo'ysin Alpomish,
Baxmal uyda mahkam qisar belingnan...⁸*

Ushbu parcha tahlilidan avval bir xalq qo'shig'ini keltirsak:

*O'zim qarchig'ay bo'lsam,
Ilintirsam o'zingga.
Bilagingga talpinsam,
Meni olsang qo'yningga.⁹*

In this excerpt, the Prophet is represented through the symbol of the moon, and the four caliphs through four stars. This reflects the influence of the Islamic layer within the epic — though in our view, in the pre-Islamic period the symbol of the moon signified a patron deity. Over time, the moon became a fully poetic symbol representing the beloved. However, in certain examples it has retained its earlier traces. In the treasury of folk songs, particularly in *yor-yor* songs, there are a great many examples that begin with the traditional line "One star before the moon." For instance:

*Oy oldida bir yulduz,
Oy bolasi, yor-yor.
Kelinchakni so'rasang,
Boy bolasi, yor-yor.*

In the song, the father or mother is likened to the moon, and the child to a star. Parents, too, are guardians for their child. In terms of its historical foundation, this song is a remarkable example of semantic parallelism connected with mythology.

In the excerpt we have cited, the horse Boychibor is represented through the symbol of an eagle. There are certain reasons for this as well. Boychibor is a winged steed (*tulpar*) — he can fly like a bird. Furthermore, he is the defining companion of the main hero and sometimes, as in a horse race for example, steps into the foreground while Alpomish comes in second place.

Folklorist Sh. Turdimov states that in folk lyric songs, birds — crows, geese, ducks, cranes, and swallows — are messenger symbols, and substantiates this through analysis.¹⁰ The eagle and

⁸ Alpomish. – B.99–100.

⁹ Оқ олма, қизил олма. Ўзбек халқ кўшиқлари / Тўпловчи М. Алавия. – Тошкент: Фан, 1972. – Б.17.

¹⁰ Турдимов Ш. Поэтические символы в узбекских народных лирических песнях: Дисс... канд. филолог. наук. – Ташкент, 1987; Турдимов Ш. Том устига том солдим // Ёшлик. – Тошкент, 1988. №7. – Б.75–76; Турдимов Ш. Бирнинг минг жилваси // Ёшлик. – Тошкент, 1987. №5. – Б.70–71.

falcon that appear in Barchin's dream are symbolic messengers. For this reason, Barchin does not transform into a bird in her dream but remains in human form. There is yet another aspect in Barchin's dream connected with Boychibor. In whatever symbolic form he may appear in a dream, Boychibor is in essence a winged steed.

Scholar M. Alaviya notes that if a horse is seen in a dream, it is interpreted as the fulfillment of one's wish.¹¹ Characteristically, in folk songs as well, a horse is interpreted as the symbol of a wish and as the poetic counterpart of the beloved:

Sarhovuz bo 'yida sariq ot ko 'rdim,

Sollonib chiqqanim bir murod ko 'rdim.

Bedov otni sug 'ormoqqa chiqqanda

*Yorginamni mash 'al chiroqday ko 'rdim.*¹²

Just as in the epic "*Alpomish*," in "*Kuntug'mish*" as well the *chiltans* put the main characters to sleep and unite their spirits in dreams, celebrating their union.

*"The two played together, and Xolbeka took the ring from the lord's finger and placed it on her own. (That same night Kuntug'mish saw such a dream as well.) At this point both of them awoke. The lord heaved a deep sigh, unable to share this sorrow with anyone; when he looked at his signet ring, it was a different ring — and when he pressed it as a seal upon paper, the name of Xolbeka appeared."*¹³

In this example, what is significant for our observation is the detail of the ring in the dream. Without dwelling at length on the meanings attributed to a ring in mythological thinking and on views regarding its magical properties, it is clearly evident in this passage that the ring possesses a magical quality. According to the content of the epic, the ring serves as a symbol of love and family, and functions as a poetic detail confirming that the marriage of the heroes was solemnized (recited) by the *chiltans*. That is to say, both the dream in the epic and the ring along with its properties are products of mytho-poetic thinking.

According to our informant Momoxol Norova from Kashkadarya, the following interpretations exist for seeing a ring in a dream: if an unmarried young man sees a ring in his dream, he will soon marry; if he is already married, he will have a child. If an unmarried girl sees a ring in her dream, matchmakers will come to her and her wedding will take place soon; if she is already married, she will have a child. Whether the child will be a girl or a boy depends on the dreamer's zodiac sign (*muchal*) — that is, if their sign is among the clean animals such as horse, sheep, rabbit, or chicken, a boy will be born; if it is among animals such as mouse, snake, or monkey, a girl will be born.

Now let us examine some of the meanings conveyed by the ring as a poetic symbol in folk songs:

¹¹ Алавия М. Ўзбек халқ кўшиқлари. — Тошкент: Фан, 1959. — Б.31.

¹² Оқ олма, қизил олма. Ўзбек халқ кўшиқлари / Тўпловчи М. Алавия. — Тошкент: Фан, 1972. — Б.121.

¹³ Эргаш Жуманбулбул ўғли. Булбул тароналари. Беш томлик. — Тошкент: Фан, 1971. Т.1 — Б.175–176.

*Kuyov pochcham qo'lida**Talpinar qush, yor-yor.**Kelinoyim uzugi**Toza kumush, yor-yor.**Qo'lidagi kumushi**Davlat bo'lsin, yor-yor.**Qo'ndirilgan qushlari**Farzand bo'lsin, yor-yor.¹⁴*

Of course, one cannot tell a folk song performer to sing it this way or that. However, the second verse of this example of ours:

*Qo'lidagi kumushi**Farzand bo'lsin, yor-yor.**Qo'ndirilgan qushlari**Davlat bo'lsin, yor-yor, –*

when sung thus, it would accord both with our informant's interpretation and with the epic tradition. It is well known that in many Uzbek fairy tales and epics, when the king of a certain land dies, the *davlatqush* (bird of fortune) is released and a new king is chosen. For example, if we refer to the epic "Kuntug'mish" mentioned above: "...*Buvraxon the king died. At that time the custom for kings was as follows: a bird called the davlatqush would be released, and whomever it landed upon would be made king*".¹⁵ In the epic, Kuntug'mish becomes the king of Shahri Zangar by virtue of the *davlatqush*. The following examples also confirm the accuracy of our thoughts regarding the meanings conveyed by the ring symbol in folk songs:

*Chimildiqning tagidan**Topdik uzuk, yor-yor.**Qaysi boyning qizisan,**Ko'zi suzuk, yor-yor?*

¹⁴ Тўй муборак: Ёр-ёр / Нашрга тайёрловчи Охунжон Сафаров. – Тошкент: Маънавият, 2000. – Б.57.

¹⁵ Эргаш Жуманбулбул ўғли. Булбул тароналари. Беш томлик. – Тошкент: Фан, 1971. I том. – Б.290.

*Qo'limdagi qo'sh uzuk, qo'lim uzuk,
Ko'zim senga tushibdir, ko'zi suzuk...*¹⁶

A folk song, unlike a fairy tale or epic, has no plot and does not dwell on details. Understanding the relationship between its symbols and dreams depends in large measure on the listener's imagination, knowledge, and level of comprehension.

The comparison of symbols found in epics and songs that we have examined demonstrates the necessity of studying more deeply and specifically the direct or indirect influence of the dream phenomenon on folk lyrics as well.

Naturally, we are far from claiming that all symbols in folk songs emerged under the influence of dreams. However, it cannot be denied that dreams have served as an important historical and creative foundation in this regard.

To further substantiate our conclusion, let us dwell on the commonalities expressed by several more symbols found in dream interpretations and in songs. As a rule, a desert or wilderness seen in a dream is interpreted as a sign of separation. In songs as well, they convey this very same symbol:

*Qizil gulim, qizil gulim,
Ajab bevaqt xazon bo'lding.
Meni cho'llar aro tashlab,
O'zing yo'lga ravon bo'lding.*

If a chest seen in a dream is interpreted as a sign of a wedding, in folk songs it becomes a symbol of the family upon which marriage is founded:

*Ikki sandiq ro'baro' ro'y beradi, yor-yor.
Ikki quda teng turib qo'y beradi, yor-yor.*¹⁷

In the treasury of Uzbek folk lyric songs, examples beginning with the phrase "Beyond the rivers..." are very frequently encountered. Both in dreams and in songs, a river or the far side of waters signifies separation, while a bridge signifies union.

Russian folklorist V.I. Yeromina also notes that crossing water (a river, sea, or canal) in folk tradition serves as a symbol of marriage.¹⁸ A bridge is the most convenient means of crossing from one bank to the other:

¹⁶ Тўй муборак: Ёр-ёр / Нашрга тайёрловчи Охунжон Сафаров. – Тошкент: Маънавият, 2000. – Б.68, 147.

¹⁷ Оқ олма, қизил олма. Ўзбек халқ кўшиқлари / Тўпловчи М. Алавия. – Тошкент: Фан, 1972. – Б.20, 165.

¹⁸ Еремина В.И. Ритуал и фольклор. – Л.: Наука, 1991. – 208 с.

*Taxta-taxta ko 'prikday**Taxting bo 'lsin, yor-yor.**Payg 'ambarning qiziday**Baxting bo 'lsin, yor-yor.*¹⁹

Since the unity of dream and song manifests itself above all in the harmony of symbols, it is necessary to emphasize yet another aspect. This concerns the question of their difference from real life in terms of imaginative and artistic-aesthetic contemplation. For example, in real life people drink tea every day, or some people live by a river and see the other side of it daily. It should be stressed that tea, a river, a bridge, a ring, a bird, and the like acquire symbolic meaning only in dreams and in folk songs — in folklore in general. In ordinary everyday life they carry no meaning beyond their practical necessity.

In a legend recorded by Ch. Valikhanov, it is said that in ancient times a song flew over the earth and taught people to sing. It was as delicate and beautiful as a woman. In whatever place the song paused longer and rejoiced, the people there lived with many children and in prosperity.²⁰

To conclude, one more common feature characteristic of both dream and song is that, since ancient times, neither submits to the laws of ordinary logic — the fruit of sound reason. From the standpoint of poetics, those aspects of folk songs that do not submit to the laws of logic can now be understood by us as poetic tropes and products of imagination. Yet what is interesting is that mythological thinking is likewise a mode of thinking in which imagination holds sway. One of the important characteristics of this mode of thinking is the absence of boundaries and impossibilities for desire.²¹ Dreams occur beyond our will. Folk songs — particularly traditional examples in which traces of mythological thinking are perceptible — are likewise beyond our will. For both, just as in myth, anything is possible. That which does not exist simply cannot be said not to exist.

To understand the symbols in dreams and folk songs — in oral folk art in general — what is needed is not only facts and scholarly observations, but also deep poetic sensibility and the noble imagination that accompanies a person throughout their entire life.

At the historical foundation of a great many poetic symbols in Uzbek folk songs lies the influence of dreams and the mythological thinking surrounding them.

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¹⁹ Остонаси тиллодан. Тўй кўшиқлари. – Тошкент: Фан, 1992. – Б.25.

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